

Dipole approach for calculation the electric field in a system of three parallel conducting cylinders

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Highlights

The successive dipole simulation method (SDSM) is drastically simplified in a three-cylinder system.

A theoretical formula for the exponential convergence rate of the SDSM is obtained.

A formula for the number imaging stages is proposed to ensure the required accuracy.

A series of numerical examples of accuracy/convergence, benchmark simulations are given.

The offset effect in a two-core shielded cable is investigated in detail.

A B S T R A C T

In the case of a system of three infinitely long parallel cylindrical conductors, there is a hidden geometric symmetry, which leads to the fact that all fictitious line dipole charges and their successive images lie on a circular curve in a 2D plane. Then the location of any of dipole charges is determined by the polar angle only and it becomes possible to find a theoretical estimate of the rate of exponential convergence of the successive dipole simulation method (SDSM). The simplicity and effectiveness of the described formulation of the SDSM have been demonstrated by comparison with other methods.

Keywords:

Potential problems; Dipole simulation method; Charge simulation method; Convergence analysis; Complex fictitious charges; Shielded cables.

1. Introduction

Potential problems of a two-dimensional system of three infinitely long parallel cylindrical conductors are well known in science and engineering, since this simple structure is often used in practice, e.g., as the simplest configuration of a three-phase line, shielded or lying on the inner surface of a conducting cylinder two-core power or communication cables, two-wire overhead DC or AC power lines placed above a ground plane as the limiting case of a circular cylinder. The electromagnetic problem for a two-cylinder system, as known, has a closed-form solution (see, e.g., [1,2]). In the case of multiple parallel cylindrical conductors, several analytical approaches have been presented in the literature; however, they do not give a closed form expression for the electric field distribution. Some of them assume a Fourier surface charge density on the conductors and solve the infinite determinants [3,4] or used the integral-equation method, in which the unknown functions are the densities of the induced electric charges on the surfaces of the conductors, leading to solutions in the form of infinite series whose coefficients can be calculated algebraically [5]. The methods

presented in [6,7] are based on the theory of automorphic functions and give the electric field distributions in a system of parallel cylindrical conductors in terms of series expansions whose elements depend on the two-dimensional realization of the group of automorphisms. In [8], the null-field integral equation method is proposed to solve the Laplace problems with circular boundaries, in which, the null field equation of the Green representation formulas is used, and the fundamental solutions are replaced by their infinite expansion series. An analysis of the error of the null-field integral equation method and numerical comparisons of its results with some boundary methods are given in [9]. Application of two-dimensional translation addition theorems for scalar Laplace functions in polar coordinates to electrostatic problems for various positions of parallel circular cylindrical conductors is described in [10]. Numerical results are obtained by appropriate truncation of the infinite series in the expressions for the harmonic fields and in the addition theorems.

The method of successive images [11] and the successive dipole simulation method (SDSM) [12] can be considered as special exact cases of the charge simulation method (CSM), in which for a system of N infinitely long cylinders, fictitious $M = N$ line charges and $M = N(N-1)/2$ fictitious line dipoles are introduced, respectively. At any k -th stage of the successive imaging process, the image charges in the system of conductors obtained in the previous stage are resolved into a new image charges at well-defined positions, and the total number of images will be $N(N-1)^k$ charges and $N(N-1)^{k+1}/2$ dipoles, respectively, but the number of unknown simulated values of charges in the system will remain the same, i.e. equal M . In contrast to the CSM, the SDSM immediately gives the exact solution for the case of two arbitrary cylinders with a known potential difference between them.

All of the methods mentioned are exact in the sense that they lead to exact solutions, but their application requires truncating the number of elements, stages, or terms in the series used in the solution process. These methods differ in a number of properties, such as ease of formulation and programming, the requirement of computer time and memory, rate of convergence (especially in cases where cylindrical conductors are very close to each other or to the shield), and suitability for simulating floating potential electrodes and an unbounded field region. In a practically important case of a system of three cylindrical conductors and some others (for example, if the centers of identical cylinders are the vertices of a regular polygon), in the SDSM the dipole charges and their successive images lie on a circular curve and in a coordinate system with the origin at the center of this circumcircle, the location of any of these charges is determined by the polar angle only. The transition to this coordinate system leads to a significant simplification and conciseness of the algorithm for determining the positions of new charge images at each stage of the imaging process. It also provides a useful theoretical estimate of the rate of exponential convergence of the SDSM. Sample calculations for the electric field distribution in a system of three circular conducting cylinders outside each other or two contained inside a third conducting cylinder with predefined potential differences between them are presented and the possibility of obtaining accurate results with a minimum computational effort is shown for various values of these parameters.

The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, the center and radius of the circumcircle, where the fictitious line dipole charges of the three-cylinder system are located, are determined. The application of the found symmetry in the SDSM is briefly described. A general theoretical formula is derived for the rate of convergence of the method. In section 3, the identity of the calculation results of the original and described formulations of the SDSM is demonstrated for the case of three identical cylinders forming an equilateral triangle. A comparison is also made with the analytical results obtained in [10] for the case of three cylinders with different radii. The maximum electric field and its relative error as a function of time were analyzed in a three-phase AC system. The exponential convergence of SDSM is shown for various configurations of two offset cylindrical conductors inside a cylinder both theoretically and numerically. In the last section, a few concluding remarks are made.

2. Methods

2.1. Geometric preliminaries

The problem in the complex plane with three non-intersecting circles O_1 , O_2 , and O_3 with radii r_1 , r_2 , and r_3 centered at positions \mathbf{O}_1 , \mathbf{O}_2 , and \mathbf{O}_3 , respectively, is shown in Figs. 1a and 1b. Let $O_1O_2O_3$ be a non-degenerate triangle, while the circles do not necessarily outside each other, as can be seen in Figs. 1a and 1b. The pairs of points $(\mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_{-1})$, $(\mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_{-2})$, and $(\mathbf{R}_3, \mathbf{R}_{-3})$ in Figs. 1a and 1b are the image points (or inverse points) with respect to the pairs of circles (O_1, O_2) , (O_2, O_3) , and (O_3, O_1) , respectively. For convenience, consider these paired circles as virtual pairs (O_1, O_{-1}) , (O_2, O_{-2}) , and (O_3, O_{-3}) , respectively. The corresponding inverse points of the j -th pair ($j = 1, 2, 3$) satisfy the system of equations

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{R}_j = \mathbf{O}_j - \frac{r_j^2}{\mathbf{O}_j^* - \mathbf{R}_{-j}^*} \\ \mathbf{R}_{-j} = \mathbf{O}_{-j} - \frac{r_{-j}^2}{\mathbf{O}_{-j}^* - \mathbf{R}_j^*} \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where the symbol $*$ is used to denote complex conjugation. The solution of this system of equations leads to known results [1,2]

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{R}_j = \mathbf{O}_j + \frac{1}{2\mathbf{D}_j^*} \left(r_j^2 - r_{-j}^2 + \left(D_j^2 \mp \sqrt{(D_j^2 - (r_j + r_{-j})^2)(D_j^2 - (r_j - r_{-j})^2)} \right) \right) \\ \mathbf{R}_{-j} = \mathbf{O}_{-j} + \frac{1}{2\mathbf{D}_j^*} \left(r_j^2 - r_{-j}^2 - \left(D_j^2 \mp \sqrt{(D_j^2 - (r_j + r_{-j})^2)(D_j^2 - (r_j - r_{-j})^2)} \right) \right) \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{D}_j = \mathbf{O}_{-j} - \mathbf{O}_j$, $D_j = |\mathbf{D}_j|$, r_j and r_{-j} are the radii of the circles O_j and O_{-j} whose centers are located at the points \mathbf{O}_j and \mathbf{O}_{-j} , respectively; the lower sign is taken when one circle is inside the other and the upper sign is taken when they are external to each other.

Fig. 1. Arrangement of inverse points and circumcircle ρ for the cases when three circles are outside each other (a) and two are inside the third circle (b).

Using the positions of inverse points defined by formulas (2), it can be shown, after lengthy but simple calculations, that the circumscribed circles of the triangles $R_1R_2R_3$ and $R_{-1}R_{-2}R_{-3}$ coincide and, therefore, the hexagon $R_1R_{-1}R_2R_{-2}R_3R_{-3}$ is circumscribable with the center

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{O}_\rho &= \frac{\mathbf{I}}{4S} \left(\mathbf{O}_1 \left(|\mathbf{O}_3|^2 - |\mathbf{O}_2|^2 - r_3^2 + r_2^2 \right) + \mathbf{O}_2 \left(|\mathbf{O}_1|^2 - |\mathbf{O}_3|^2 - r_1^2 + r_3^2 \right) + \mathbf{O}_3 \left(|\mathbf{O}_2|^2 - |\mathbf{O}_1|^2 - r_2^2 + r_1^2 \right) \right), \\ S &= \frac{\mathbf{I}}{4} \left(\mathbf{O}_1 (\mathbf{O}_3^* - \mathbf{O}_2^*) + \mathbf{O}_2 (\mathbf{O}_1^* - \mathbf{O}_3^*) + \mathbf{O}_3 (\mathbf{O}_2^* - \mathbf{O}_1^*) \right),\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the imaginary unit, S is the oriented area of the triangle $O_1O_2O_3$ (positive for a negative triangle, as $O_1O_2O_3$ on Fig. 1a, and negative for a positive triangle, as $O_1O_2O_3$ on Fig. 1b). This result seems to be unknown. Note that the distance between the circumcenters of the hexagon and the triangle $\Delta = O_1O_2O_3$ (i.e., when $r_3 = r_2 = r_1 = 0$ in (3)), can be written as

$$\mathbf{O}_\Delta - \mathbf{O}_\rho = \frac{\mathbf{I}}{4S} \left(\mathbf{O}_1 (r_3^2 - r_2^2) + \mathbf{O}_2 (r_1^2 - r_3^2) + \mathbf{O}_3 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) \right).\quad (4)$$

The radius of the circumcircle of the hexagon can be determined using the positions of any three inverse points, for example, as

$$\begin{aligned}\rho &= \frac{1}{4S_\rho} |\mathbf{R}_2 - \mathbf{R}_1| \cdot |\mathbf{R}_3 - \mathbf{R}_2| \cdot |\mathbf{R}_1 - \mathbf{R}_3|, \\ S_\rho &= \frac{\mathbf{I}}{4} \left(\mathbf{R}_1 (\mathbf{R}_3^* - \mathbf{R}_2^*) + \mathbf{R}_2 (\mathbf{R}_1^* - \mathbf{R}_3^*) + \mathbf{R}_3 (\mathbf{R}_2^* - \mathbf{R}_1^*) \right).\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

2.2. An alternative (not based on direct calculations) proof that the hexagon $R_1R_{-1}R_2R_{-2}R_3R_{-3}$ is circumscribable

Let a circumcircle ρ with the center at the point $\mathbf{O}_\rho = 0$ and radius ρ is defined, for definitely, by the triangle $R_1R_{-1}R_3$, and the inverse points $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1}$ are written as $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1} = \rho \cdot \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \alpha_{\pm 1})$. Since \mathbf{R}_{-1} is the image of \mathbf{R}_1 , from the first of Eqs. (1) follows

$$\mathbf{R}_1 = \mathbf{O}_1 - \frac{r_1^2}{\mathbf{O}_1^* - \mathbf{R}_{-1}^*}.\quad (6)$$

Using the angle $\psi = (\alpha_1 + \alpha_{-1})/2$, the points $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1}$ can be expressed in the form $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1} = \rho \cdot z \cdot \exp(\pm \mathbf{I} \cdot \phi)$, where $\phi = (\alpha_1 - \alpha_{-1})/2$ and $z = \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \psi)$. Then the solution of Eq. (6) can be written as

$$\mathbf{O}_1 = z \cdot \left(\rho \cdot \cos(\phi) \pm \mathbf{I} \cdot \sqrt{\rho^2 \sin^2(\phi) + r_1^2} \right)\quad (7)$$

and, obviously, $O_1 = |\mathbf{O}_1| = \sqrt{\rho^2 + r_1^2}$. Of course, as $\text{Re}(\mathbf{O}_1) = \text{Re}(\mathbf{R}_1) = \text{Re}(\mathbf{R}_{-1})$, the point \mathbf{O}_1 is lying on the line joining the inverse points \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_{-1} . For the case shown in Fig. 1a, when circles are external to each other, $|\mathbf{R}_1 - \mathbf{O}_1| < r_1$ and, therefore, it is necessary to select the upper sign in formula (7) and, conversely, in the case of Fig. 1b, when two circles is inside the circle O_1 , select the lower sign.

Let an arbitrary point Γ lies on the circumcircle ρ (i.e., $\Gamma = \rho \cdot \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \gamma)$, where γ is a real number). For the circle O_1 , from the second of Eqs. (1) it follows that the image of this point will be located at the point

$$\Gamma_{-1} = \mathbf{O}_1 - \frac{r_1^2}{\mathbf{O}_1^* - \Gamma^*} = z \cdot \rho \cdot \frac{1 - \left(\cos(\phi) \pm \mathbf{I} \sqrt{\sin^2(\phi) + \frac{r_1^2}{\rho^2}} \right) (\cos(\gamma_0) - \mathbf{I} \sin(\gamma_0))}{\cos(\phi) \mp \mathbf{I} \sqrt{\sin^2(\phi) + \frac{r_1^2}{\rho^2}} - \cos(\gamma_0) + \mathbf{I} \sin(\gamma_0)},\quad (8)$$

where $\gamma_0 = \gamma - \psi$. It is easy to see from Eq. (8) that

$$\frac{|\Gamma_{-1}|}{\rho} = 1 \quad (9)$$

and, therefore, for any point Γ on the circumcircle ρ its image Γ_{-1} with respect to the circle O_1 is displayed on this circumcircle. Likewise, the inverse point \mathbf{R}_{-3} is also displayed on the circumcircle ρ which was defined by the triangle $R_1R_{-1}R_3$. Because the pairs of points $(\mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_{-1})$ and $(\mathbf{R}_3, \mathbf{R}_{-3})$ are the inverse points also with respect to the pairs of circles (O_1, O_2) and (O_3, O_1) , respectively, the coordinates of centers \mathbf{O}_2 and \mathbf{O}_3 (in form like (7)) can be determined the same way as for point \mathbf{O}_1 . According to proven the intersections of the line O_2O_3 with the circumcircle ρ are the inverse points with respect to the pair of circles O_2 and O_3 . From the uniqueness of the positions of the inverse points for circles (O_2, O_3) it follows that they are the point \mathbf{R}_2 and its image \mathbf{R}_{-2} . Thus, indeed, all six inverse points $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1}$, $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 2}$, and $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 3}$ lie on the circumcircle ρ (as it was announced above based on the results of the direct calculations).

2.3. Introduction of a new coordinate system with origin at point $\mathbf{O}_\rho = 0$

Next it is convenient to use the complex plane with the origin at the circumcenter \mathbf{O}_ρ . The advantage of using the new coordinate system is that the locations $\mathbf{R}_{\pm i}$ of the i -th pair of inverse points can be expressed using only variables $\alpha_{\pm i}$ as $\mathbf{R}_{\pm i} = \rho \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \alpha_{\pm i})$, where the polar angles $\alpha_{\pm i}$ are the angles from the real-axis (like the angles γ and θ in Figs. 1a and 1b and β below) defined using values $\mathbf{R}_{\pm i}$ and \mathbf{O}_ρ in the old coordinate system as follows:

$$\alpha_{\pm i} = -\mathbf{I} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{\mathbf{R}_{\pm i} - \mathbf{O}_\rho}{\rho} \right). \quad (10)$$

Since six original points $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1}$, $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 2}$, and $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 3}$ lie on the circumcircle ρ , formed by the system of circles O_1, O_2 , and O_3 , all their successive images lie on the circumcircle ρ (see, e.g., (9) for arbitrary point and circle O_1). This result is known in the trivial case of three identical cylindrical conductors located at the vertices of an equilateral triangle [13], where $\rho^2 = L^2/3 - r^2$, L is the distance between centers of circles, r is the radius of circles.

To find the position of the image of any point on the circumcircle with respect to one of the circles O_1, O_2 , and O_3 , it is necessary only to draw a line through this point and the center of the particular circle. The intersection of this line with the circumcircle gives the image of this point. From the consideration of a point near the circle O_i , $i = 1, 2$, or 3 , and its "nearly mirror" image, it follows that the points of intersection of the circumcircle with these circles are at right angles. The points $\mathbf{O}_\rho, \mathbf{O}_i$, and the intersection of circles O_i and O_ρ forms a right-angled triangle, and therefore (as for O_1 , see (7))

$$O_i = |\mathbf{O}_i| = \sqrt{\rho^2 + r_i^2}. \quad (11)$$

Thus, an arbitrarily given point $\Gamma = \rho \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \gamma)$ will have the images $\Gamma_{-i} = \rho \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \gamma_{-i})$, where γ_{-i} is simple defined for each i -circle, $i = 1, 2$, and 3 , by the formula

$$\gamma_{-i} = -\mathbf{I} \ln \left(\frac{\Gamma_{-i}}{\rho} \right) = -\mathbf{I} \ln \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\mathbf{O}_i - \frac{r_i^2}{\mathbf{O}_i^* - \Gamma^*} \right) \right) = \beta_i - \mathbf{I} \ln \left(\frac{O_i - \rho \exp(\mathbf{I}(\gamma - \beta_i))}{\rho - O_i \exp(\mathbf{I}(\gamma - \beta_i))} \right), \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{O}_i = O_i \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \beta_i)$, polar angles β_i are defined using values \mathbf{O}_i and \mathbf{O}_ρ in the old coordinate system as follows:

$$\beta_i = -\mathbf{I} \ln \left(\frac{\mathbf{O}_i - \mathbf{O}_\rho}{|\mathbf{O}_i - \mathbf{O}_\rho|} \right). \quad (13)$$

2.4. Estimation of the convergence of successive images of pairs of close points on the circumcircle

The ratio of an arc of length $ds = \rho d\gamma$ on the circumcircle \mathbf{p} to its inversion $ds_{-i} = \rho d\gamma_{-i}$ (which is also placed on the circumcircle) with respect to the circle O_i will be defined by the formula

$$F_i(\gamma) = \frac{ds}{ds_{-i}} = \left(\frac{d\gamma_{-i}}{d\gamma} \right)^{-1} = -\frac{O_i^2 - 2O_i\rho \cos(\gamma - \beta_i) + \rho^2}{O_i^2 - \rho^2}. \quad (14)$$

The maximum and minimum values of the parameter $|F_i(\gamma)|$ correspond to the conditions $|\gamma - \beta_i| = \pi$ and $\gamma - \beta_i = 0$, respectively, and can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} |F_{i\max}| &= \frac{O_i + \rho}{|O_i - \rho|}, \\ |F_{i\min}| &= \frac{|O_i - \rho|}{O_i + \rho}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In the case of pairs of inverse points (α_i, α_{-i}) and (α_{-i}, α_i) with respect to the circles O_i and O_{-i} , respectively, the average value of F_{iav} for two successive imaging $ds_i \rightarrow ds_{-i}$ (with respect to the circle O_{-i}) and $ds_{-i} \rightarrow d\tilde{s}_i$ (with respect to the circle O_i) will be

$$F_{iav} = \frac{ds_i}{d\tilde{s}_i} = \sqrt{F_{-i}(\alpha_i) \cdot F_i(\alpha_{-i})}. \quad (16)$$

The condition $1/F_{iav} < 1$ ensures that the images of pairs of close points on the circumcircle will vanish in the infinite process of successive imaging with respect to the circles O_i and O_{-i} .

2.5. New geometrical formulation of the SDSM in the case of three cylinders

Step 1. The SDSM [12] is a semi-analytical method based on fictitious line dipole charges and their images. In the first stage of successive imaging of the method, the distributed surface charges of the system of N infinite parallel cylinders are approximated by $M = N(N-1)/2$ fictitious line dipoles with line charge densities of $\pm\lambda_1, \pm\lambda_2, \dots, \pm\lambda_M$ placed respectively at the pairs of inverse points $\mathbf{R}_{\pm 1}, \mathbf{R}_{\pm 2}, \dots, \mathbf{R}_{\pm M}$ defined by formulas (2).

Step 2. As shown above, in a practically important case of a system of three cylindrical conductors and some others (e.g., if the centers of four or more identical cylinders lie on a circular cylindrical surface), the fictitious dipole charges and their images are placed on a circular cylindrical surface. This allows the use of a coordinate system adapted to the symmetry of the problem. In a 2D coordinate system with the origin at the center of this cylinder, the polar angle remains the only variable that fully describes the location of the charges of fictitious line dipoles.

Since all further calculations will be performed in this new coordinate system, the positions of N cylinders and M pairs of the fictitious line dipole charges, defined on Step 1, should be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{O}_i = O_i \cdot \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \beta_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{\pm i} = \rho \cdot \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \alpha_{\pm i}), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, M, \quad (18)$$

where O_i , the radius ρ of the circumcircle, polar angles β_i and $\alpha_{\pm i}$ are defined by (11), (5), (13), and (10), respectively.

Step 3. Several numerical examples in [12], covering different cases of conditions and geometry, demonstrate that the maximum error of the approximate solution of the SDSM decays exponentially as stage m of the image formation process increases.

Estimate (16) for pairs of close points on the circumcircle makes it possible to estimate the rate of convergence A in the approximate dependence $O(A^{-m})$ for the maximum errors of the potential and electric field. Then, using the numerical proportionality coefficients from the examples in [12], the

optimal number m_{opt} that provides the required accuracy can be taken as the nearest larger integer obtained from the distribution:

$$m = 1 - \frac{1.5 + \ln(\varepsilon_f)}{\ln(\min_{1 \leq i \leq N} F_{i \text{ av}})}, \quad (19)$$

where ε_f is the desired maximum relative error for the electric field in the system, $F_{i \text{ av}}$ is given by (16). Usually, at this value of m_{opt} , the accuracy of calculating the potential and other quantities is higher.

Step 4. Although separately the surfaces of each virtual pair of cylinders with the fictitious line dipoles are equipotential surfaces, the equipotentiality of the surface of each cylinder containing $N - 1$ virtual dipole charges will be disturbed by the action of other $K_2 = (N - 1)(N - 2)/2$ fictitious dipoles (formed by the other cylinders). The disturbing effect of any such dipole with charges $(\lambda, -\lambda)$ can be eliminated by appropriate placing of the K_2 pair of image charges $(-\lambda, \lambda)$ in the next (second) stage of successive imaging of the SDSM. The total number of dipoles (fictitious dipoles and image dipoles) in the system will be $M_2 = N(N - 1)^2/2$. The effect of the introduced new K_2 image dipoles can be taken into account in other $N - 1$ cylinders the same way to keep the equipotentiality of the ones in the third stage of the SDSM.

In general, in the m -th stage, for each cylinder the number of newly formed image dipoles is determined as

$$K_m = (N - 1)K_{m-1} = (N - 1)^{m-1}(N - 2)/2, \quad m = 3, 4, \dots \quad (20)$$

Their charge points \mathbf{R}_s^m and \mathbf{R}_{-s}^m , $s = 1, \dots, N \cdot K_m$, are easily defined by formula (12). The total number of dipoles becomes equal to

$$M_m = M_{m-1} + N \cdot K_m = N(N - 1)^m/2, \quad m = 3, 4, \dots \quad (21)$$

Step 5. In the $m = m_{\text{opt}}$ stage, once the positions of the dipoles are determined, the potential at any point \mathbf{R} can be found by superposition

$$\varphi_m(\mathbf{R}) = \sum_{k=1}^M P_k^m(\mathbf{R}) \lambda_k + C, \quad m = m_{\text{opt}}, \quad (22)$$

where $P_k^m(\mathbf{R})$ is the potential coefficient, defined recursively as follows:

$$P_k^m(\mathbf{R}) = P_k^{m-1}(\mathbf{R}) - \frac{(-1)^m}{2\pi\varepsilon\varepsilon_0} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq s \leq N \cdot K_m \\ \lambda_s = \lambda_k}} \ln \frac{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_{-s}^m|}{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_s^m|}, \quad m = 2, 3, \dots, m_{\text{opt}}, \quad (23)$$

$$P_k^1(\mathbf{R}) = \frac{1}{2\pi\varepsilon\varepsilon_0} \ln \frac{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_{-k}|}{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_k|},$$

where ε_0 is the permittivity of vacuum, ε is the relative permittivity. The uniqueness theorem states that the value of the constant C in Eq. (22) can be set to any value because it makes no contribution to the electric field, since the addition of a constant makes no difference to the gradient, thus, one can choose $C = 0$ for the potential to vanish at infinity.

To find the values of the dipole charges, pairs of collocation points \mathbf{S}_j and \mathbf{S}_{-j} are selected on the surfaces of each j -th pair of virtual cylinders ($j = 1, \dots, M$). The required collocation points can be selected, for example, on the lines of the shortest distance between the surfaces of the cylinders. Then the potential differences between the testing points can be calculated on m_{opt} stage by superposition of all the dipole charges effects:

$$U_j = \varphi_m(\mathbf{S}_{-j}) - \varphi_m(\mathbf{S}_j) = \sum_{k=1}^M P_{jk}^m \lambda_k, \quad m = m_{\text{opt}}, \quad (24)$$

where λ_k is the unknown dipole charge of the k -th fictitious dipole and

$$P_{jk}^m = P_k^m(\mathbf{S}_{-j}) - P_k^m(\mathbf{S}_j). \quad (25)$$

When Eq. (24) is applied to M pairs of collocation points, it leads from stage $m = m_{\text{opt}}$ to the following system of M linear equations for M unknown fictitious line charges

$$\mathbf{P} \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \mathbf{U}, \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{P} = \{P_{jk}^m\}$, $m = m_{\text{opt}}$, is the potential coefficient matrix (with dimension $M \times M$, $M = 3$ in the case of $N = 3$ cylinders), $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_M]^T$ is the column vector of the unknown charges, $\mathbf{U} = [U_1, U_2, \dots, U_M]^T$ is the column vector of the known applied voltages for pairs of the collocation points on the surfaces of virtual cylinders.

Step 6. Once the system (26) has been solved, the potential can be calculated by Eq. (22) and the electric field at any point \mathbf{R} is defined as a derivative of the potential:

$$\mathbf{E}_m(\mathbf{R}) = -\text{grad } \varphi_m(\mathbf{R}) = \sum_{k=1}^M H_k^m(\mathbf{R}) \lambda_k, \quad m = m_{\text{opt}}, \quad (27)$$

where the field coefficient matrix $H_k^m(\mathbf{R})$ is given recursively by

$$H_k^m(\mathbf{R}) = H_k^{m-1}(\mathbf{R}) - \frac{(-1)^m}{2\pi\epsilon\epsilon_0} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq s \leq N \cdot K_m \\ \lambda_s = \lambda_k}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_s^m}{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_s^m|^2} - \frac{\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_{-s}^m}{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_{-s}^m|^2} \right), \quad m = 2, 3, \dots, m_{\text{opt}}, \quad (28)$$

$$H_k^1(\mathbf{R}) = \frac{1}{2\pi\epsilon\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_k}{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_k|^2} - \frac{\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_{-k}}{|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}_{-k}|^2} \right).$$

3. Verification of the computational procedure and parametric investigation

To verify the efficiency and accuracy of the SDSM with the above suggested computational procedure of imaging, different arrangements of three parallel cylinders have been considered. In this paper, for definiteness, the required six collocation points were selected on the lines of the shortest distance between cylinder's surfaces. The permittivity of vacuum ϵ_0 is taken as $8.854 \cdot 10^{-14}$ F/cm and the relative permittivity ϵ of the surrounding medium is set to 1. The potential φ_i of the i -th cylinder was calculated as the average value of $\varphi_i(\theta)$ at four points on the surface at azimuth angles $\theta = 0, \pi/2, \pi$, and $3\pi/2$. All calculations were carried out using Maple® with precision of 40 decimal digits.

Note that recently [14], SDSM estimates of corona onset voltage have been compared with experimental results in an electrode system with 10 cylinders and 9 (and also 19) wires for different discharge gaps.

3.1. Verification for the case of identical cylinders forming an equilateral triangle

The validity of the developed algorithm was verified on a test example from [12] with a system of three identical cylindrical conductors of radius $r = D/2$ centered at the vertices \mathbf{O}_i of an equilateral triangle, where $\mathbf{O}_i = 3^{-1/2} L \cdot \exp(\mathbf{I} \cdot \beta_i)$, $\beta_i = \pi/6 \cdot (13 - 4i)$, $i = 1, 2$, and 3 , L is the distance between centers of circles. Since the center of the circumcircle $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ is at the origin (i.e., $\mathbf{O}_\rho = 0$, see (4)), the radius of the circumcircle is $\rho = \sqrt{L^2/3 - r^2}$ (see (11)). The applied voltages to the electrodes are given as $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = U$ and $\varphi_3 - \varphi_1 = -U$. Calculations are carried out for various values of the spacing $S = L - D$, while maintaining a fixed distance L between the centers of the cylinders and changing the S/D ratio from 0.01 to 10. Due to the symmetry of the system under study, the calculated potential φ_1 and the net charge of the 1-st cylinder $A_1 = \lambda_1 - \lambda_3$ are equal to zero.

The accuracy of the modified SDSM is demonstrated in Fig. 2 for the case $S/D = 1$. The normalized potential difference $|\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 - U|/U$, maximum relative errors $\delta\varphi_1/U$ and $\delta\varphi_2/U$, and as well as the field deviation $E_{2\tau}/E_{2n}$ (the maximum ratio of the tangential ($E_{2\tau}$) and normal components (E_{2n}) of the field vector on the surface of the 2-nd cylinder) are shown up to stage $m = 12$. As seen from Fig. 2, all types of errors decay exponentially at approximately the same rate with increasing stage m of the imaging process. As can be seen from Fig. 2, formula (19) with $F_{1av} = 13.9$ gives good estimates for the number of required imaging stages. The results obtained using formula (12) to determine the charge points in the successive dipole imaging process are identical to those obtained in [12], where, however, the maximum stage was limited to $m = 7$.

Fig. 2. Decay of the errors with stage m of the SDSM for the case $S/D = 1$.

The numerical results presented for cases $S/D = 0.01, 0.1, 1, \text{ and } 10$ in Table 1 show a decrease in the numerical convergence of the method with decreasing S/D ratio. A more detailed analysis, similar to that shown in Fig. 2, together with the analysis performed earlier in [12], showed that the errors obey an approximate exponential dependence $O(A^{-m})$, where $A \approx 1.36, 2.3, 13, 480, \text{ and } 40800$ for $S/D = 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, \text{ and } 100$, respectively. Already in the second stage, the errors are sufficiently small for S/D , greater than 10. Formula (16) gives the change in the moment of the microscopic dipole (per unit length) at the stage of dipole imaging. It can be seen that each successive dipole is smaller in magnitude. In the completely symmetric geometry used, the choice of any pair of inverse points α_i and α_{-i} ($i = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$) in formula (16) leads to values of F_{iav} close to A : 1.33, 2.43, 13.9, 482, and 40800 for the S/D series above, respectively. Thus, the numerical convergence of the method is directly determined by the decrease in the dipole moment in the successive imaging process. Indeed, the exponential convergence of an approximate solution to a potential problem with increasing the number of elements, stages, or terms in the series used numerically has been estimated many times, but the author is not aware of any publications that have established the theoretical formulas (like (16) or (19)) concerning exponential convergence in an n -connected domain, where $n \geq 3$.

An electric field factor [15] in Table 1, showing the degree of non-uniformity of an electric field, is defined as follows:

$$f = \frac{E_{\max}}{E_{\text{av}}}, \quad (29)$$

where E_{\max} is the maximum value of the electric field in the system, $E_{\text{av}} = |V|/d_{\min}$, d_{\min} is the minimum distance between the two conductors (which define E_{\max}), having a potential difference of V . For the tested arrangement of cylinders $E_{\text{av}} = 2U/S$. Table 1 shows that the electric field factor f tends to unity as S/D tends to zero. For $S/D = 0.01$ the deviation from a uniform field ($f = 1$) is only 0.33%.

Table 1.

Accuracy of the SDSM, net charge A_2 , and electric field factor f for different S/D (stage $m = 12$).

S/D	$\delta\varphi_1/U$	$\delta\varphi_2/U$	$ \varphi_2 - \varphi_1 - U /U$	$E_{2\tau}/E_{2n}$	$A_2/U, 10^{-12} \text{ C/cm/V}$	f
0.01	$0.24 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$0.27 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$0.28 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$0.42 \cdot 10^{-2}$	5.4634	1.0033
0.1	$0.55 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.45 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.10 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.27 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.49904	1.033116
1	$0.53 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$0.35 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$0.18 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$0.58 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.43227978	1.3178951
10	$0.31 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$0.16 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$0.86 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$0.19 \cdot 10^{-30}$	0.18015687	3.5471362

3.2. Comparison with the analytical results obtained in [10]

The proposed method has been applied to an equilateral triangle cylinder arrangement presented in [10] in which the axes of cylinders of radii $r_1 = 1 \text{ cm}$, $r_2 = 2 \text{ cm}$, and $r_3 = 3 \text{ cm}$ form a triangle with sides 10 cm each. The charges, per unit length, placed on conductors 1, 2, and 3 are $Q_{1M} = 1 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ C/cm}$, $Q_{2M} = -2 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ C/cm}$, and $Q_{3M} = 1 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ C/cm}$, respectively. The calculated potentials on the cylinders for the translational method with the series truncations of $K = 15$ are $\{\varphi_{1M} = 40.2284 \text{ V}$, $\varphi_{2M} = -54.8842 \text{ V}$, $\varphi_{3M} = 20.4456 \text{ V}\}$. These results were obtained by solving system of $N(2K + 1) = 93$ linear equations.

The calculated potentials for the SDSM with $\{U_1 = \varphi_{2M} - \varphi_{1M}$, $U_2 = \varphi_{3M} - \varphi_{2M}$, $U_3 = \varphi_{1M} - \varphi_{3M}\}$ for considered geometry at stage $m = 12$ are $\{\varphi_1 = 40.22840321732 \text{ V}$, $\varphi_2 = -54.88419678268 \text{ V}$, $\varphi_3 = 20.44560321732 \text{ V}\}$ and the electrostatic capacities of the cylinders (defined as the ratio of the line charge of each cylinder to its potential) are $\{C_1(m = 12) = 0.24857526180243 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ C/cm/V}$, $C_2(m = 12) = -0.36439568532467 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ C/cm/V}$, $C_3(m = 12) = 0.489091886025114 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ C/cm/V}\}$.

The calculation accuracy of the two methods (SDSM and translational method) for the capacities of the cylinders is shown on Fig. 3. For comparison, the maximum ratios of the tangential and normal components E_{it}/E_{in} of the field vector on the surface of the i -th cylinder ($i = 2$ and 3) are also shown. The convergence of the SDSM results in dependence on stage m occurs approximately as $O(A^{-m})$ and for stage $m \geq 4$ the results are more accurate than for the translational method with the series truncations of $K = 15$. The predicted value $F_{2\text{av}} = 14.43$ is close to the numerical value $A = 14.75$ and formula (19) gives good estimates for the number of required imaging stages (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Accuracy of two methods. $\delta C_i(m) = |C_i(m)/C_i(m=12) - 1|$, $\delta C_{iM}(K=15) = |Q_{iM}/\varphi_{iM}/C_i(m=12) - 1|$.

3.3. Efficient calculation of AC electric field in a system of three parallel conducting cylinders by SDSM using complex fictitious charges

The field distribution for an applied low-frequency sinusoidal voltage can be calculated in an efficient way by the use of complex fictitious charges [16,17]. This is possible because the fictitious charges also change sinusoidally with an angular frequency same as that of the applied voltage. Therefore, to calculate the distribution of the low-frequency field, it is necessary to solve the linear equation (26) with complex sinusoidal voltage \mathbf{U} . Then, in particular, the above results in Section 3.1 for the case of identical cylinders forming an equilateral triangle can be considered as the results for the time $t = 0$, assuming that the column vector of the known potential differences \mathbf{U} between the cylinders defines as

$$\mathbf{U} = 2U \exp(\mathbf{I}\omega t) \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \exp\left(\mathbf{I}\frac{\pi}{3}\right) \\ \exp(\mathbf{I}\pi) \\ \exp\left(\mathbf{I}\frac{5\pi}{3}\right) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

with ω is the angular velocity. Complex charges derived from Eq. (26) and subsequently the computed potentials and the electric field are all complex quantities which also vary sinusoidally with time. One should keep in mind, however, that only the real parts of these complex quantities have physical significance. Since the potentials of the conductors vary sinusoidally with time, the simulation accuracy is time dependent. The time behaviors of the maximum normalized electric field E_{\max}/E_{av} (for 2-nd cylinder) at stage $m = 7$ and its relative error, defined as dimensionless

$\delta E_{\max}/E_{\max} \equiv |E_{\max}(m=7)/E_{\max}(m=12) - 1|$, are shown in Fig. 4 for the case $S/D = 0.1$. The maximum values of the electric field in Fig. 4, equal to the electric field factor f in Table 1 for $S/D = 0.1$, correspond to the maximum values of U_2 ($\omega t = 0, \pi, \text{ and } 2\pi$) and U_1 ($\omega t = 2\pi/3 \text{ and } 5\pi/3$).

Fig. 4. Variation of the normalized maximum electric field E_{\max}/E_{av} and its relative error $\delta E_{\max}/E_{\max}$ as functions of time ωt for 2-nd cylinder at stage $m = 7$. $S/D = 0.1$, $E_{\text{av}} = 2U/S$.

3.4. Two identical offset cylindrical conductors inside a conducting cylinder

The next test example involves an offset system of two identical infinitely long parallel cylindrical conductors with radii $r = 0.1 \cdot R$ inside a cylinder with radius R whose centers are located at points with complex coordinates $\mathbf{O}_1 = 0$, $\mathbf{O}_2 = -d/2 + d_x - \mathbf{I}H$, and $\mathbf{O}_3 = d/2 + d_x - \mathbf{I}H$, where $d = 0.8 \cdot R$, $d_x = 0.2 \cdot R$, and $H = 0.3 \cdot R$ (see Fig. 5). Potential differences between the electrodes are given as $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = U$ and $\varphi_3 - \varphi_1 = -U$.

Fig. 5. Geometrical configuration of offset cylindrical conductors inside a cylinder. The angle θ measured from the direction of the vector $\mathbf{O}_2\mathbf{O}_3$.

In this asymmetrical system the calculated potential of the shielded cylinder is found to be $\varphi_1(m = 12) = 0.29488563U$ (i.e., non-zero), but, of course, for the complete system, the sum of the charges of all three conductors is equal to zero, i.e., $A_1 + A_2 + A_3 = 0$. The numerical convergence of the method is demonstrated in Fig. 6. In addition to the maximum relative errors for the cylinder's potentials and the field deviations $E_{2\tau}/E_{2n}$ and $E_{3\tau}/E_{3n}$, there the relative error of maximum electric field E_{\max} in the system is also shown. The normalized electric field $E_i(\theta)/E_{av}$ on the surfaces of i -th cylinder, $i = 1$ (on the inner surface), 2, and 3 are shown in Fig. 7. For the tested arrangement $E_{av} = U/S_{31}$. Since the normal component of the field E_{1n} on the inner surface of the 1-st cylinder changes sign at angles θ about -1.27 and 1.08 radian ($|\mathbf{E}(\theta)| = 0$, see Fig. 7), the ratio $E_{1\tau}/E_{1n}$ has a singularity and is not shown in Fig. 6.

As can be seen from Fig. 6, all types of error exponentially decay at approximately the same rate with increasing stage m of the imaging process. The errors obey the approximate dependence $O(A^{-m})$, where A is approximately $5.3 \div 6.1$. The A values were found to be in good agreement with the predicted $F_{3av} = 5.42$ determined by formula (16) for the inverse points with respect to the cylinders O_1 and O_3 , which contribute the most to the error. As can be seen from Fig. 6, formula (19) gives good estimates for the number of required imaging stages. The errors become very small already in the fourth or fifth stages.

Fig. 6. Changes of the normalized potential difference $|\varphi_i - \varphi_1 - U|/U$, maximum error $\delta\varphi_i/U$, field deviation $E_{i\tau}/E_{in}$ for the i -th cylinder ($i = 1, 2, 3$), and the relative error of the maximum electric field $\delta E_{2max}/E_{2max}$ in the system with stage m of the SDSM. $H/R = 0.3$, $d_x/R = 0.2$.

Fig. 7. Normalized electric field $E_i(\theta)/E_{av}$ on the inner surface of cylinder 1 (dashed line), around cylinders 2 (thin solid line) and 3 (thick solid line) in stage $m = 12$ of the successive imaging process. $H/R = 0.3$, $d_x/R = 0.2$.

The following series of test cases includes a symmetrical offset system of two identical infinitely long parallel cylindrical conductors with radii $r = 0.1 \cdot R$ and the fixed distance $d = 0.8 \cdot R$ between them inside a cylinder with radius R , as in the second test, but with $d_x = 0$ and different offset distances H (see Fig. 5). Potential differences between the electrodes are given as in the second test (i.e. $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = U$ and $\varphi_3 - \varphi_1 = -U$).

Table 2 contains the value of the net charge for 2-nd cylinder A_2 , the electric field factor f , the maximum values of the electric field and potential errors, and the actual (A) and predicted (F_{1av}) convergence rates in the system for various values of normalized offset distances H/R (or S/D). The parameter H/R is associated with the S/D value by the formula

$$\left(\frac{H}{R}\right)^2 = \left(1 - \frac{D}{R} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{S}{D}\right)\right)^2 - \left(\frac{d}{R}\right)^2, \quad (31)$$

where $D = 2r$, $S = S_{12} = S_{31}$. To use formula (12) to determine the charge points in the successive dipole imaging process, the triangle $O_1O_2O_3$ must be a non-degenerate triangle, that is, the offset distance H must be non-zero, but it can be arbitrarily small (for example, as $H/R = 1 \cdot 10^{-10}$ in Table 2). As expected, the accuracy of the estimates decreases with decreasing S/D , and the electric field factor f tends to unity when S/D tends to zero. The errors of all types decay exponentially with the approximate dependence $O(A^{-m})$ when stage m of the image formation process increases. It can be seen from Table 2 that the A ratios for the potential error $\delta\varphi_1$ are in reasonable agreement with the predicted F_{1av} determined by formula (16) for inversed points with respect to the cylinders O_1 and O_2 (or O_1 and O_3 due to symmetry), which contribute the most to the error.

Table 2.

Net charge A_2 , electric field factor f , maximum potential errors ($\delta\varphi_1/U$ with the actual (A) and predicted (F_{1av}) convergence rates, $\delta\varphi_2/U$, and $|\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 - U|/U$), and the field deviation $E_{2\tau}/E_{2n}$ for different values of the normalized offset distance H/R (stage $m = 12$).

H/R (S/D)	$A_2/U,$ 10^{-12} Q/cm/V	f	$\delta\varphi_1/U$	A	F_{1av}	$\delta\varphi_2/U$	$ \varphi_2-\varphi_1-U /U$	$E_{2\tau}/E_{2n}$
$1\cdot 10^{-10}$	0.31705739	3.2119635	$0.30\cdot 10^{-10}$	7.18	8.38	$0.16\cdot 10^{-10}$	$0.15\cdot 10^{-10}$	$0.28\cdot 10^{-10}$
0.01	0.31706747	3.2111832	$0.30\cdot 10^{-10}$	7.18	8.38	$0.16\cdot 10^{-10}$	$0.15\cdot 10^{-10}$	$0.28\cdot 10^{-10}$
0.3 (2)	0.32762565	2.5898716	$0.92\cdot 10^{-10}$	6.49	7.47	$0.48\cdot 10^{-10}$	$0.43\cdot 10^{-10}$	$0.82\cdot 10^{-10}$
(1)	0.38332958	1.6703589	$0.39\cdot 10^{-8}$	4.59	5.00	$0.22\cdot 10^{-8}$	$0.17\cdot 10^{-8}$	$0.30\cdot 10^{-8}$
(0.1)	0.96634	1.06935	$0.75\cdot 10^{-4}$	1.81	1.80	$0.59\cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.16\cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.22\cdot 10^{-4}$
(0.01)	2.9566	1.00698	$0.25\cdot 10^{-2}$	1.29	1.21	$0.24\cdot 10^{-2}$	$0.17\cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.25\cdot 10^{-3}$

4. Conclusions

It has been shown in this paper that all six mutually inverse points in a system of three arbitrary circular curves form a circumscribed circle. In addition, it was shown that for any circular curve (of three in the system), the image of any point on this circumcircle will lie on the same circumcircle. Explicit analytical formulas are determined for the parameters of the circumcircle and inverse points. The revealed properties lead to a significant simplification and conciseness of the algorithm for determining the positions of new charge images at each stage of the imaging process when the SDSM is applied to the practically important case of a system of three infinitely long parallel cylindrical conductors and some others. Furthermore, a theoretical formula is derived for the rate of exponential convergence of the SDSM, which is important for estimating the number of required imaging stages.

The simplicity and effectiveness of the described formulation of the SDSM were demonstrated in a test with three identical cylinders forming an equilateral triangle; the calculation results were identical to those of the original formulation of the SDSM. Moreover, the modified SDSM was applied to systematically study the offset effect in a system of two cylindrical conductors inside a conducting cylindrical shield. It was also shown that the SDSM with complex charges can be effectively used to analyze three-phase AC fields.

The exponential convergence of the results with dependence on the stage m , the possibility of using a predefined number of $m = m_{opt}$ to ensure the required accuracy, and the minimum requirements for computational resources make the developed method yield benchmark solutions, which would be useful for establishing the range of validity of the existing methods.

The SDSM in the described formulation can be applied to a system with $N > 3$ arbitrary cylinders, but then $C_N^3 = N(N-1)(N-2)/6$ circumcircles must be taken into account.

The high efficiency of the developed method in cases where some of the cylindrical conductors are very close to each other, provides the basis for future work, which will focus on accurate calculations for a roller-type electrostatic separator for separating wire particles.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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